

MELvan: An AI-Assisted Approach to Capturing Program Impact

Reducing Cognitive Load for Leaders Documenting Impact on the Go

Guest

Christina Honeywell, MSc, CCGC

Client:

Co-Director, Precision Child and Youth Mental Health Collaboratory
Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario (CHEO) Research Institute

Challenge:

“In meetings, I often hear something and think: we need to capture this—it matters for our program evaluation. But I don't have time to open the evaluation framework on the spot and figure out where it fits. The moment passes—and so does the chance to reflect, or document unintended and emergent consequences of our program, whether positive or negative. I wish I had a robot assistant—MELvan*—I could take everywhere to classify what I hear and see, in real time, into our outputs and outcomes.

*MELvan is a wordplay on Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL)

Proof of Concept Solution:

An AI assistant (MELvan) powered by ChatGPT and an evaluation workflow

Knowledge Base: Evaluation Frameworks · Program Knowledge (Public Domain, no PHI or CCI*) · Continuous Feedback

Workflow: Capture → Classify & Log → Bimonthly Log Review → Integrate Learnings into Evaluation Framework

Feedback to MELvan to Improve Classification Accuracy

Leaders

- Capture short notes or photos during meetings & daily work
- No need to open the evaluation framework or decide where it fits on the spot

MELvan

- Classifies content into outputs, outcomes, indicators, or flags a gap and proposes a new entry
- Generates a structured log with confidence scores & short rationale

Review & Use

- Entries are reviewed every two months by program leadership & the evaluation consultant
- Feedback is provided to MELvan
- Insights feed monitoring, learning, and episodic evaluation projects

Preliminary Results

- Accuracy:
 - Classification: 77%
 - Mapping : 42%
- Harmful content: None
- Hallucination : 0%
- Deferred engagement ability: 3 out of 3
- Usefulness Overall: Yes

Next Steps

- Develop and implement MELvan in alignment with CHEO's AI principles & framework
- Evaluate performance overtime
- Share/present/learnings & Rubric

*PHI (Personal Health Information) CCI (Commercially Confidential Information)

Citation: Salehi, R., Honeywell, C., & Pajer, K. (2026). MELvan: An AI-Assisted Approach to Capturing Program Impact Reducing Cognitive Load for Leaders Documenting Impact on the Go. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18902209>

Contact: Roxana Salehi, PhD, Vitus Consulting, roxana@vitus.ca

Evaluation Rubric (Forthcoming).

Contact:

Roxana Salehi, PhD

roxana@vitus.ca